

Chemical-etching-based observation on spherulitic and interfacial morphologies of fiber reinforced thermoplastics

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Questions? Remarks?
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Introduction

- Some compression-molded glass fiber reinforced polypropylene (GF/PP) unidirectional (UD) laminates were manufactured under different cooling rates, and the wedge peel tests on those samples showed a significant difference in the interlaminar bond strength.

Fig. 1 Wedge peel strength of UD GF/PP laminates manufactured under different cooling rates

Fig. 2 The temperature profiles

Table 1 The transient cooling rates

	at 200 °C	at 166 °C	at 102 °C
SC	51 K/min	42 K/min	23 K/min
FC	604 K/min	484 K/min	206 K/min

- Related characterization indicated the effect of crystallization: lower crystallinity, smaller crystallite size, fine α -PP, and the existence of β -PP...

Fig. 3 The XRD profile (left) and the degree of crystallinity of the FC and SC samples

Experiments and results

Chemical etching (CE)

- The permanganic acid solution preferentially etches the amorphous part of the PP in the spherulites, in such a way that the lamellae then clearly appear under SEM.

Fig. 4 The flowchart of CE and sequential SEM observation (left) and schematic of semi-crystalline structure (right)

PP spherulitic morphology

- Central radial lamellae, sheaf-like structures, with two perpendicular lamellae brunches
- Mostly immature spherulites, and FC samples have smaller spherulitic sizes.

Fig. 5 Typical PP spherulitic morphologies

Fiber nucleation

- FC: Lamellae can grow along/spreading the GF surface (better F/M contact) as well as toward the matrix area due to relatively sufficient growing space;
- SC: Lamellae grow perpendicularly to the GF surface (limited contact at lamellae edges) due to suppression by their neighborhoods.

Fig. 6 Fiber-nucleation phenomenon in FC samples (left) and SC samples (right)

Fiber/matrix morphology

- Less nucleation and crystal growth time under FC;
- FC: Semi-spherulites on GF surface, with more amorphous PP and fewer spherulites;
- SC: (like-) transcrystalline structures on GF surface.

Fig. 7 Different fiber-matrix morphologies in FC samples (left) and SC samples (right)

- The delamination is dominated by (near GF surface) matrix failure, along grain boundary!

Fig. 8 (near GF surface) matrix failure in FC samples (left) and SC samples (right)

- FC: Interlocked grain boundary, with more amorphous PP in between spherulites, higher F/M adhesion.
- SC: Relatively flat and straight grain boundary parallel to GF surface (also to wedge peel direction), poor F/M adhesion.

Fig. 9 Different grain boundaries in FC samples (left) and SC samples (right)

Conclusion

- With CE, spherulitic and interfacial morphologies of GF/PP delaminated samples were directly revealed.
- Different cooling rate makes differences in fiber-matrix morphologies, resulting in different (near GF surface) interphases/structures and fracture propagation paths, and thus a different level of wedge peel strength, as well as bond strength.

Fig. 10 Schematic of different fracture paths in FC samples (left) and SC samples (right)